

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TECHNOLOGIES TO THE FIELD OF GEOLOGY.

Nurmurodov J.N

Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi,
Department of Artificial intelligence

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14214490>

Abstract. *In today's world, there is a growing need for artificial intelligence technologies to identify and classify subsurface mineral resources. Traditional methods have proven ineffective in classifying ore layers, particularly for uranium ore. Therefore, in our scientific research, we will use an RNN (Recurrent Neural Network) to classify uranium ore layers. We will employ a quadratic B-spline function as the activation function for the RNN. Firstly, we will study the parameters of the device that generates signals identifying uranium ore layers and collect data in tabular form from vertical depth measurements. Using the collected data, we will develop a classification algorithm to determine whether uranium ore is present in each layer. Due to the large volume of data obtained from wells, we will identify the characteristic feature of the layer containing uranium ore as the maximum spectral value determined by the gamma-neutron method.*

Keywords: *machine learning, output regression, gamma-neutron, RNN, AI.*

1. Introduction

Researchers around the world are conducting extensive studies in the field of geophysics. Especially in detecting underground mineral resources, many challenges arise. Determining the depth at which radioactive elements emitting radiation are located has remained a problematic issue to date. Various algorithms have been proposed by scientists to solve this problem. However, due to significant errors in current models and methods used for predicting the location of chemical elements in the earth's crust based on surface radiation signals, there is a need for new models and methods. One of these methods is machine learning. In machine learning, linear regression is one of the fundamental algorithms studied initially. When applied to different datasets, it has various advantages and limitations. It primarily serves to establish a linear relationship between local and global variables.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Method for Determining the Layer Containing Ore:

The gamma-neutron (GN) method is considered effective for detecting uranium ore among underground mineral resources. This method is complex and highly effective for determining the chemical composition of rock formations, based on the detection of an impulsive gamma ray flux. In this process, the impulsive gamma rays interact with the rock formation over a short period, leading to the simultaneous emission of neutrons in a radioactive reaction. An example of this is the reaction process used to detect uranium ore. The process of determining the ore layer typically involves the following steps: Boreholes are drilled into the ground, and the GN measurement device is lowered into these boreholes. The impulsive gamma ray flux emitted by the device's generator interacts with ores located within a maximum distance of 40-60 cm from the borehole.

Using the signal values provided in Figure 1, we organize the necessary data into a tabular format. The layers that show the highest spectral values are considered to be the layers containing uranium ore. We present the signal values obtained from each borehole in the following tabular format. The radiation levels obtained from the surface and underground layers are used to train a neural network. The gradient values of the neural network, resulting from their difference, are collected (wes).

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Statistical Models

Statistical models play a crucial role in understanding the relationship between subsurface and surface data. These models help quantify relationships and predict future conditions. Below we review the importance of statistical models in this context, as well as examples and methods.

Quantifying relationships: Statistical models can quantify the strength and nature of relationships between surface and subsurface data.

Predicting future trends. By analyzing historical data, statistical models can predict future ore deposits, which is important for planning and management.

3.2. Basic statistical Architecture for Training Signals from Surface and Underground Layers in an RNN

Anomalous changes in geophysical processes can be used to make predictions. Typically, these predictions can provide information about where the highest concentrations of valuable minerals are located and their reserve volumes. Predictions utilize anomalous changes in the Earth's electromagnetic and gravitational fields, anomalous changes in the ionosphere, seismic conditions (noise), various acoustic vibrations, and radiation rays. For training the neural network, based on the analyses, we choose a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN). To improve the accuracy of the neural network, we use the B-spline function as the activation function. To this end, we develop the architecture and algorithm of the Recurrent Neural Network.

Figure 1. Proposed Recurrent Neural Network Architecture

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. Testing Phase of the Ore Layer Classification Algorithm

We will test the results obtained using the constructed neural network model and algorithm.

Table 4

For testing, the surface layer radiation level is X_i in sample units (MeV).

№	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.	13.	14.	15.	16.
1.	123	123	122	123	125	125	125	127	127	126	125	125	125	125	126	125
2.	126	125	125	126	124	123	123	123	125	125	125	125	124	123	124	123
3.	125	126	124	124	124	127	124	124	123	123	124	124	125	124	124	125
4.	127	126	126	127	128	128	128	129	129	128	127	127	128	127	127	127
5.	124	124	124	123	124	124	125	126	126	127	126	125	126	127	127	128
6.	125	126	123	123	123	123	123	123	123	124	123	124	124	123	123	124

Using the differences in radiation levels provided in Tables 1 and 2, we will employ the neural network weight values from Table 3 to verify the accuracy of predictions based on the sample data in Table 4. For testing, we will use 25% of the values from the 64x64 matrix obtained for the sample data, resulting in a 16x16 matrix.

Table 5. For testing, the underground layer radiation level is Y_i in sample units (MeV).

№	1.	2.	3.	4.	5.	6.	7.	8.	9.	10.	11.	12.	13.	14.	15.	16.
1.	142	143	143	143	144	144	144	145	144	144	145	144	142	144	144	144
2.	164	164	164	165	167	167	167	165	166	167	166	167	166	165	164	164
3.	166	166	165	163	161	160	159	158	158	158	158	158	158	158	160	161
4.	169	169	169	170	170	170	171	171	172	172	172	173	172	170	169	170
5.	162	161	161	162	162	162	162	162	161	162	161	162	163	163	163	163
6.	162	162	162	162	163	163	162	162	163	163	163	162	161	162	163	162

$$\Delta_1 = |164 - 163,884723| = 0,115277$$

(4)

levels. Formula 4: Calculating the absolute error in predicting underground radiation levels using surface radiation

$$\Delta_2 = \left(1 - \frac{|256 - 52|}{256}\right) \cdot 100\% = 20,3125 \%$$

(5) Formula 5:

Calculating the relative error in predicting ore layers without drilling to depth using surface

radiation levels. In this case, with 256 radiation values derived from a 16x16 matrix, it is possible to identify 52 locations where drilling to depth can be performed, with an absolute error of 0.112.

In this graph, predictions of ore layers in new areas are made using signals obtained from ore regions without drilling boreholes. The graph indicates that the prediction error based on the Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) is quite large and has significantly increased.

Figure 5. Process of Identifying Underground Layers Based on the Proposed Recurrent Neural Network Architecture

Table 6. Evaluating Absolute and Relative Errors in the Reconstruction of Two-Variable Geophysical Signals and in

№	Si(t)	NT Si(t)	Si,j(t)	Identifying Ore Layers	
				RNN	NT Si,j(t)
Δ_1	0.015	0.0087	0.4110	0.62	0.01
Δ_2	3.5%	1.7%	4.3%	5.1%	3.2%
τ_1	2.3ms	2.7 min	6.9ms	7.3min	7,5-9 min

The results in the table show the error rates in the process of reconstructing two-dimensional ZG signals. The data indicates that using the proposed RNN architecture improves the prediction accuracy by 0.20%.

Conclusion

Today, artificial intelligence methods are increasingly being integrated into various fields. The effectiveness of these methods lies in their ability to minimize errors by utilizing probabilistic values. By considering spectral coefficients and frequency parameters resulting from the spread of ionizing radiation, it is methodologically possible to obtain values close to those obtained from experimental measurements. This methodology demonstrates the ability to identify the location and dimensions of valuable radioactive ores underground without the need for drilling. Based on this methodology, the accuracy of software-generated results can be improved by up to 20% when compared to real measurement values. This approach holds promise for evaluating radiation background values dependent on spectral energy and frequency of ionizing radiation emitted by underground valuable radioactive ores

REFERENCE

1. Kabulov, A.; Baizhumanov, A.; Saymanov, I. Synthesis of Optimal Correction Functions in the Class of Disjunctive Normal Forms. *Mathematics* 2024, 12, 2120 doi: org/10.3390/math12132120.
2. Алберг Дж., Нильсон Э., Уолш Дж. Теория сплайнов и ее приложения. Москва: Мир, 1972. – 316 с.
3. Гребенников А.И. Об одном методе построения интерполирующих кубических и

- бикубических сплайнов на равномерной сетке // Вест. Моск. Университета, вычисл. матем. и кибер. 1978, N4, - С. 12-17.
4. Kabulov, A. ., Baizhumanov, A., & Berdimurodov, M. . (2024). On the minimization of k-valued logic functions in the class of disjunctive normal forms. *Journal of Mathematics, Mechanics and Computer Science*, 121(1), 37–45. doi.org/10.26577/JMMCS202412114
 5. D. Singh, M. Singh, and Z. Hakimjon, “Evaluation methods of spline,” in *SpringerBriefs in Applied Sciences and Technology*, 2019.
 6. Zaynidinov, H., Nurmurodov, J., Qobilov, S. Digital Signal and Image Processing Using Neural Networks. *Proceedings of the Seminar on Information Systems Theory and Practice, ISTP*, November 2023, pp. 3-8, doi: [10.1109/ISTP60767.2023.10426883](https://doi.org/10.1109/ISTP60767.2023.10426883).
 7. Zaynidinov, H., Nurmurodov, J., Qobilov, S. Application of Machine Learning Methods for Signal Processing in *Piecewise-Polynomial Bases Proceedings - 9th IEEE International Conference on Information Technology and Nanotechnology, ITNT 2023* doi: [10.1109/ICISCT52966.2021.9670135](https://doi.org/10.1109/ICISCT52966.2021.9670135).
 9. Завьялов Ю.С., Квасов Б.И., Мирошниченко В.Л. Методы сплайн-функций. Москва: Наука, 1980. - 352 с.
 10. Хайкин С. Нейронные сети: полный курс. 22-е изд. пер. с англ.- М. Изд. дом «Вильямс» 2006-452с
 11. Musayev A.A, Serdyukov Yu.P. Modeli signalov s optimalnymi karakteristikami vo vremennoy i chastotnykh oblastiakh // *Matematicheskiye metody v tekhnike i tekhnologiyah: sb.tr. XXIX mejdunar. nauch. konf.: v 12 t. T. 3 / Saratov. gos. texn. un-t. 2016. S. 116-123.*
 12. Proletarskiy A.V. Algoritmy preobrazovaniya spektrov v bazisax Haar i Uolsha.//*Avtomatizatsiya. Sovremennyye tekhnologii. M: Izd-vo «Innovationnoye mashinostroyeniye». 2018. T. 72, № 10. S. 453-461*
 13. Rodionov Ye. A. O primeneniі veyvletov k sifrovoy obrabotke signalov // *Izv. Sarat. un-ta. Nov. ser. Ser. Matematika. Mexanika. Informatika. 2016. T. 16, вып. 2. S. 217-225.*
 14. Roldugin S.V. Sifrovaya obrabotka signalov. Uchebnoye posobiye / - Voronej: Nauchnaya kniga, 2016. - 144 s. ISBN 978-5-4446- 0908-8
 15. Svinin S.F. Bазисные сплайны в теории отсчетов signalov. Sankt-Peterburg: Nauka,2003. – 117 str.